

An Analysis of the Socio-psychological Barriers in the Course of Communicative Competence in the English language

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Abstract: The primary goal of this research work is to comprehend the socio-psychological barriers that arise during the course of communication. Social psychology is the scientific and technical study of how people's beliefs and feelings are impacted by the definite, actual, and implied pressure of other people. Whereas social variables are defined as broad elements at the level of human society that are connected to the social structure and social activities that have a significant impact on individuals. The communication processes that take place in people's daily lives are heavily impacted by socio-psychological obstacles. Socio-psychological obstacles play a crucial role in the persistence of impulsive contentious situations. On the other side, they provide an essential contribution to impeding the execution of communication procedures. Overcoming socio-psychological obstacles is essential for achieving personal and professional goals, as well as forming friendly terms and relationships with one another. It is critical for individuals to put in place measures and procedures aimed at overcoming socio-psychological hurdles. Understanding the significance of socio-psychological obstacles to communication, and strategies to overcome socio-psychological barriers to communication are the key issues addressed in this study work.

Keywords: Socio-Psychological Barriers, Communication, Individuals, motivation, Norms, Principles, language acquisition.

I. INTRODUCTION

The scientific study of how the beliefs and feelings of individuals are impacted by the actual, imagined, and suggested pressure of other persons is referred to as social psychology. Social variables are broad factors at the level of human society that are connected to the social structure and social processes that have a significant impact on individuals. Socio-psychological obstacles have a significant effect in the persistence of headstrong disputes. On the other hand, they play an important role in imposing impediments to the execution of communication procedures. Individuals as human beings are studied in relation to the power of the socio-psychological context. Individual behaviour is central to the theories of this illness. To put it another way, psychological factors, personality characteristics, perception, and cognition are all crucial when it comes to individual and social behaviour. There are a variety of reasons why people allow social influences to impact their beliefs and behaviour. One of the most important reasons is that in order to obtain the acceptance of the group's members, one frequently complies with its rules and values. However, it is critical to increase the sense of cooperation. When individuals cooperate with one another, it leads to a uniformity of beliefs, culminating in a phenomenon known as groupthink. The feature of cooperation will make an essential contribution to giving answers to individual difficulties as well as reducing socio-psychological situations. To be effective, communication systems must be free of impediments to the free flow of information. The socio-psychological obstacles are regarded as the most difficult hurdles to communication, and it is critical to use ways and tactics to overcome them.

II. UNDERSTANDING THE MEANING OF SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL COMMUNICATION BARRIERS

Socio-psychological communication obstacles may be defined as the source of issues encountered during the execution of communication procedures. Individual psychology is recognised as the key component that gives birth to socio-psychological obstacles. When one believes that the other person is more competent and experienced, communication with him will be more successful, especially if he is a teacher, supervisor, or employer. Individuals who believe their colleagues or fellow students are more qualified and skilled than them, on the other hand, are unlikely to be engaged and may even have sentiments of animosity and aversion. Individuals who are pursuing career ambitions are unable to carry out their jobs and activities in isolation. It is critical for them to collaborate and integrate with others. As a result, students must recognise the sources of socio-psychological obstacles to communication and broaden their awareness of the strategies that can help them overcome them. As a result, in order to attain personal as well as professional goals, it is necessary to develop amicable terms and relationships with one another as well as overcome socio-psychological barriers.

Motivation, age, language learning experience in school and college, fear of learning a new language, anxiety in the classroom, and other socio-psychological factors are some of them. Students, for example, focus on the functional importance of English language, according to Rahman (2005). It suggests that, in our nation, English is viewed as merely a subject to pass an exam, despite the fact that this tendency is beginning to shift. They have a limited range of opportunities to practise English, and they only study English for specified goals within that range. As a result, kids prefer to acquire English based on structures and grammatical knowledge rather than comprehending how the language is used in context.

Shahed (2001), on the other hand, explores the traditions and determining elements of English language acquisition and refers to English language learners as 'subjects of horror.' The majority of individuals in our nation solely study English for academic purposes and have little or no exposure to the language. They discover English, which is a challenging language.

In terms of attitudes, natures, opinions, perspectives, and general personality qualities, each individual is unique. When two or more people communicate with each other, their beliefs, opinions, and interests may not be compatible. When these do not match, the communication process is hindered, and most people are unwilling to communicate. They do not pay attention when they are not engaged in talking, which leads to socio-psychological hurdles. When people are pursuing educational programmes or working, it is critical for them to use good communication. According to research studies, when instructors are educating or supervisors or employers are presenting information in a well-organized manner on the implementation of job tasks, students and employees pay attention, especially when they are devoted to their job duties. Normally, socio-economic barriers arise between classmates and coworkers.

III. SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL BARRIERS TO COMMUNICATION

Communication obstacles that are socio-psychological in nature can be found both within and outside the family, in educational institutions and many sorts of organisations. These barriers not only obstruct communication, but also have an impact on the general operation of businesses and educational institutions. As a result, individuals must have a thorough grasp of these limitations in order to avoid them from becoming serious issues. The following is a list of them:

Individual Attitudes and Opinions - Individual attitudes and opinions have a significant influence in affecting the communication process. When people's attitudes and opinions are good, the communication process goes smoothly. Individuals with unfavourable attitudes and opinions, on the other hand, are frequently unable to effectively implement communication methods. Individuals who are conscious of the need to learn to regulate bad attitudes and alleviate unfavourable opinions will use communication methods appropriately. Individuals must therefore have positive attitudes and ideas in order to support efficient communication. When people communicate with one another verbally or in writing, positivity and constructivism are considered essential components.

Cultural issues - Language acquisition and teaching are inextricably linked to cultural issues. The concept of the established technique of language acquisition is referred to as a cultural problem in this case. The grammar translation approach has been widely established and applied in many countries for many years. According to Alam (2015), supporters of this technique believe that learning a foreign language is accomplished by translating phrases from the target foreign language to the learner's first language and vice versa. Larsen-Freeman (2004) consider it is anticipated to learn a

language better by the study of grammatical structure of the target language since in this approach, learners would become more acquainted with grammar of the language. As a consequence, culturally, learners from our country have this perspective that learning grammar and structure is more beneficial in order to acquire a new language whereas communicative language education focuses on meaning rather than structure. If a teacher attempts to replace structural teaching with practical teaching, such as the communicative method, the instructor's popularity in the class declines, and students prefer to ignore class lectures as a result. According to Alam (2015) "The Grammar Translation Method claims that breaking the language into sections indicated by the language's grammatical categories has psycho linguistic validity". Furthermore, learning via structures only provides kids with a limited understanding of the language. Many of the patterns that pupils acquire, according to Gower, Phillips, and Walters (1983), are specific grammatical elements.

According to Diana Ansary (2012), using CLT in the classroom is difficult for instructors. Intrinsic impediments, such include passive-student traditions and unfavourable attitudes toward group work, are blamed by Rahman and Karim (2015) for the failure or partial success of the approach. Students have unfavourable feelings towards communicative and task-based learning. Adult students, on the other hand, may perceive assignments to be superfluous, as a result of which they are uninterested in and hesitant to participate in activities. As a result, the tasks and activities are unable to fulfil their objectives. Now, there is a cultural mindset influence in the EFL classroom that can be viewed as a hindrance to successful teaching. For improved quality, resolving this cultural mindset toward unusual language teaching and learning is a major challenge.

Negative emotions such as fear, wrath, frustration, despair, stress, and anxiety have an impact on an individual's psychological well-being. Individuals must reduce negative emotions such as hostility, apprehension, worry, and rage while increasing good emotions such as pleasantness and contentment in order to effectively implement communication procedures. When people speak with one another in a rage, it tends to stifle language and connections. Individuals' mental abilities are also affected by unpleasant emotions. Furthermore, they have difficulty structuring communications in an acceptable manner, and when messages are not ordered, they are difficult to understand by persons in a manageable manner. As a result, when people communicate with others both inside and outside their houses, they must maintain good emotions in order to properly arrange messages and other information and express it in a timely manner.

Individual Variations in Status- One of the most important socio-psychological impediments to communication is individual differences in status. According to research, employees in many companies are uncomfortable talking with their bosses. They frequently believe that their superiors will not contact with them in a nice manner because of their inferior status. Individuals interact with their domestic workers and service providers in terms of job obligations and other chores inside homes, on the other hand. However, they are frequently afraid to ask inquiries or communicate with them about other topics. They only speak with them when they are unsure about how to carry their work responsibilities and have queries about them. As a result, it may be claimed that status disparities are an essential socio-psychological obstacle to effective communication implementation.

Inattention - When people are conversing with others, they may be distracted by other activities. Individuals in organisations, for example, may be checking their phones or working on laptops while interacting with others. Individuals in households, on the other hand, accomplish their household responsibilities while conversing. While watching a television show or a movie, it is normal for people to converse with one another. When people are busy with other things, they can communicate in a productive way. However, when their work and activities demand their undivided concentration, they are unable to pay attention to others in some circumstances. Individuals get upset and unable to transmit or gain knowledge when they sense the desire to communicate yet others are not paying attention to them. As a result, it can be claimed that inattention is a significant socio-psychological obstacle to the proper execution of communication processes.

Impact of Age on language learning-When opposed to youthful children, adults confront a variety of challenges when learning a foreign language. One difficulty is that adult students may find themselves in a situation where their brain refuses to accept certain norms psychologically. Fossilisation is the term for this scenario. According to Han & Odlin (2006), this condition is a typical occurrence that adult learners experience when studying a second language, but it may also occur when learning a foreign language. People may have a "mental block" on processing a foreign language at times, according to Horwitz, Horwitz, and Cope (1986), even if they are good learners in other settings, where they are highly driven and really like the speakers of the target language.

Many research have looked at the causes for this barrier and how it relates to learning a new language, but it is clear from those studies that fossilisation has a strong link to new language learning. According to Selinker (1972), there is a causal link between fossilisation and the eventual achievement of language learning. This approach slows down the entire process and makes it more difficult to learn the target language fluently. In this regard, it is assumed that the percentage of adaption to a language is exactly proportionate to the learner's age, and so younger pupils learn quicker than older students (Genese & Caroline, 2006). According to Lightbown (2000), this occurs for the majority of adult learners, when the acquisition process halts or, in other words, fossilises before the learner achieves native-like competency in the target language. As a result, in the case of adult language learning, age is unquestionably a key role.

Closed Mind - A narrow-minded individual has a closed mind. Individuals that are closed-minded are prejudiced towards others and do not examine alternative viewpoints and ideas. He or she believes that his or her viewpoints are accurate. There are a variety of factors that cause people to become closed-minded. Fear of the unfamiliar, comfort with familiarity, and ego are among them. When someone is closed-minded, he shows a lack of interest in talking with others or listening to their views and viewpoints. Individuals with a closed mentality have a bad attitude that stops them from connecting with others in an orderly manner. Living in solitude, having a small social circle, and not connecting with people to a considerable level are all factors that contribute to a closed mentality. As a result, one of the most important socio-psychological impediments to effective communication is a closed mind.

Disbelief, uncertainty, and mistrust are all examples of distrust. It is suggested that one should have confidence in others in all types of relationships, including those between parents and children, husband and wife, siblings, and so on. Individuals who have faith and believe in others are better able to complete their responsibilities and activities, and communication between them is more structured. There will also be a reduction in disputes and arguments. Superiors and subordinates, as well as coworkers, must trust each other not just in their homes, but also in their workplaces. These people will need to collaborate and integrate with one another. They must have trust in people in order for their organisations to work well. On the other hand, a sense of distrust will obstruct not only terms and relationships among persons, but also the satisfactory completion of tasks and activities, as well as the attainment of personal and professional goals. As a result, mistrust is a socio-psychological roadblock in the implementation of efficient communication.

Poor Retention - In terms of message retention, poor retention is regarded as one of the key socio-psychological hurdles. When the message is essential, the recipients must remember it. They must make certain that the message is not forgotten. The communication process will not be able to take place in an acceptable manner in households as well as in other types of businesses if the individuals are unable to remember the message. As a result, it is critical for individuals to recall the message in order to effectively promote communication processes. When a communication must move through several channels inside an organisation, it is possible that it will be misplaced. This is considered to be one of the drawbacks of enhancing communication. As a result, members of organisations must demonstrate efficiency in carrying out their responsibilities. As a result, it is recognised that when a message is not conveyed properly owing to low retention, it is viewed as a socio-psychological obstacle in the process of implementing successful communication.

Anxiety and Fear of Learning a New Language- According to MacIntyre (1995), anxiety caused by the dread of learning a new language can play a significant role in the development of individual variations in language acquisition and communication. Another important socio-psychological obstacle to efficient language acquisition is this. Horwitz, Horwitz, and Cope (1986) argue that learners may experience anxiety in the classroom, preventing them from acting well in a foreign language lesson. Learners may believe that anxiousness is the most difficult obstacle to overcome in the process of learning a new language. According to Zheng (2008), it is critical to comprehend the causes and consequences of language anxiety from a contextual viewpoint in order to ease the language learning and teaching process.

Premature Evaluation - Premature evaluation is driven mostly by the predominance of unfavourable opinions about others among individuals. Individuals as well as their job performance might be affected by the presence of negative opinions. Supervisors are the ones who assess workers in terms of their behaviour and execution of job obligations inside businesses. When an evaluation is done too soon, it creates a socio-psychological barrier that limits efficient dialogue. In certain circumstances, managers make their decisions before hearing the entire message or seeing the entire work performance of the employees. In such circumstances, supervisors assume that the employees lack the necessary skills and competencies, and that they would face obstacles while doing their jobs. One of the main causes is the individuals' previous performance. Because prior performance may not be suitable, supervisors conduct the review procedure too

soon. The communication process between managers and employees cannot take place properly due to early assessment. As a result, it is possible to conclude that premature appraisal is a socio-psychological impediment to effectively implementing communication procedures.

Lack of Motivation- Adult language learners must also consider their motivation for studying English and their attitude toward the target language. Foreign language learning differs from language acquisition in that foreign language students may set out to study with specific goals in mind, such as becoming skilled in the language at an intermediate level of understanding (Dornyei, 1990, P. 6). Motivation is not a major worry in children's native language learning, according to Ushioda (2010), but it can make a big difference in how willingly and successfully they acquire foreign languages later in life. In terms of language acquisition, children have a higher degree of interest, which is one of the reasons why they are more motivated, and hence learn quicker and more readily than adult pupils.

Schimdt, Boraie, and Kassabgy (1996) conducted study in Egyptian EFL classes and found that important occupations require a certain degree of English proficiency, and professional advancement in many disciplines in Egypt is influenced by the capacity to communicate successfully in English. This sentence also applies to our situation. This desire is undoubtedly the driving reason behind continuing to study English, but it also necessitates that they be solely excited about quick and structured learning.

Interruption - A variety of reasons might cause communication processes to be disrupted. Ringing of the phone, ringing of the doorbell, someone walking into the room, noise in the neighbourhood, expressing anger and frustration, not paying attention, not maintaining eye contact, noise caused by television or radio, lack of privacy for discussion, occurrence of things that may interrupt communication, and so on are just a few examples. When one or more of these obstacles arise throughout the communication process, it is clear that it will not be well-organized. According to research performed on communication obstacles, one or more sources of interruption might cause individuals to get angry and irritated in some circumstances. Anger and frustration are seen as important roadblocks in the implementation of effective communication. As a result, it may be claimed that socio-psychological barriers occur when one or more elements of stoppage occur throughout the course of communication. The majority of the time, people are aware of how to control these circumstances.

Lack of Feedback - Within organisations and educational institutions, supervisors and instructors must offer feedback to employees on their work performance. Effective communication is recognised as the most important part of giving information, which is required for companies and educational institutions to function efficiently at all levels and for individuals to attain personal and professional goals. When supervisors and instructors offer appropriate feedback, it will assist employees become more aware of their work performance, detect irregularities, and make adjustments. As a result, effective communication procedures will be aided by appropriate feedback. Individuals, on the other hand, will not be able to produce awareness in terms of their work performances, areas where they are missing, and what steps need to be implemented to bring about improvements if feedback is not given to them in a timely manner. As a result, it may be claimed that a lack of feedback is a socio-psychological obstacle to implementing effective communication.

IV. PROCESSES TO OVERCOME SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL BARRIERS TO COMMUNICATION

Individuals both within and outside the house take steps to overcome socio-psychological barriers to communication. Individuals communicate in a variety of situations, and it is critical for them to raise awareness and improve their grasp of the measurements. The following are highlighted:

Having access to technological information - Individuals in today's world rely heavily on technology for communication as well as the execution of their professional obligations. Individuals must make use of technology when preparing reports, paperwork, or working on projects. Individuals must be well-equipped with technologies in order to make effective use of them. They enrol at training centres for this reason. Regular practise is regarded as the most important factor that individuals must acknowledge in order to improve their technical abilities. As a result, when individuals have sufficient technological information, they will be able to overcome socio-psychological communication obstacles.

Implementing Broadmindedness - Broadmindedness refers to the readiness to tolerate the actions, opinions, and perspectives of others. Individuals must practise broadmindedness in order to enhance efficient communication and overcome socio-psychological obstacles. Individuals will be able to produce constructive opinions about others and

embrace their attitudes, beliefs, and cultures as a result of this. Within organisations, for example, when individuals are working on group projects and other group members have different viewpoints and perspectives, it is necessary for members to accept them, especially if the group projects are to be completed successfully and the desired outcomes are to be achieved. As a result, applying broadmindedness will help individuals to work in collaboration with others, create well-organized communication processes, and overcome socio-psychological obstacles.

Developing Social Skills - Social skills are the ability to communicate and engage with others. Individuals of diverse ages, classifications, and backgrounds must focus on improving their social skills. Individuals who improve their social skills are better equipped to not only execute communication procedures more effectively, but also to overcome socio-psychological hurdles. Individuals who develop social skills are better able to build friendly terms and connections with people both within and outside the house. Individuals can improve efficient communication and overcome socio-psychological barriers when they establish nice and cordial terms and relationships with others. As a result, it can be claimed that improving social skills plays a significant role in overcoming socio-psychological communication obstacles.

Pedota (2007) explains how encouraging, challenging, and engaging students is critical if the instructor has high expectations for the class. This will assist students improve their academic performance as well as their ability to act morally and ethically in real life. As a result, the fear of learning English can be reduced. Finally, in order to influence students' attitudes about English, the instructor must encourage them in such a manner that they learn it not just for the purpose of passing tests or achieving a certain goal, but also as a way of life, and they begin to make efforts to enhance their exposure to English. All of these attempts to create an efficient learning environment will be in vain if the students in the classroom have or are experiencing psychological difficulties. That is why it is critical to understand about the socio-psychological issues people experience while learning a foreign language.

Getting Training - Getting training is considered essential for improving one's knowledge, skills, and capacities. Individuals are given education about work responsibilities and how to employ modern, inventive, and pioneering approaches when they are hired by firms. They are also made aware of the need of using technology to interact effectively with others, particularly their superiors and employers. Individuals are taught to understand the purpose and importance of communication with others both inside and outside the company through training. They also raise awareness about overcoming socio-psychological communication hurdles in this way. As a result, receiving training in terms of job tasks implementation, as well as other elements, will assist in effectively overcoming socio-psychological communication obstacles.

Interaction- According to Olaoluwakotansibe Agbatogun (2014), interaction between the instructor and the students is a key component of a successful educational process. It's the same with giving feedback. The teacher must keep in mind who he is providing feedback to and how he is doing so. In classes when the instructor is even younger than the kids, the teacher should be an authoritative figure who helps the children, not a dictator, while maintaining control over the classroom. He doesn't have to be the class's controller or director. If students do not have access to a stress-free atmosphere, they will get worried and their learning will suffer. Motivating and encouraging pupils, as well as offering directions, should be prioritised.

Developing Positive Attitudes Towards All Individuals - Persons must create positive attitudes in terms of all individuals in order to overcome socio-psychological obstacles and allow efficient communication. Individuals may not be satisfied with their conduct, behaviour, or work performance in some situations, but the cultivation of positive sentiments and opinions will go a long way toward promoting healthy communication processes. Positive attitudes are required not just for dealing with individuals such as teachers, supervisors, coworkers, and employers, but also for dealing with family, friends, neighbours, and community members. Individuals will contribute to enhancing their lives in this way. As a result, creating positive perspectives on all people is critical to overcoming socio-psychological obstacles and promoting good communication.

Putting Measures in Place to Reduce Interruptions - Individuals must put in place measures to reduce disruptions. When efforts to reduce interruptions are implemented, it must be guaranteed that they do not have unfavourable consequences for others or cause them to get discouraged. To put these measures in place, the first and most important stage is to identify the sources of interruptions, followed by putting the measures into effect. When an interruption is produced by a ringing phone, for example, the best course of action is to turn the phone off. When noise is inevitable in the neighbourhood, however, residents might relocate to a quieter location. As a nutshell, taking steps to reduce interruptions is critical to breaking down socio-psychological barriers and encouraging successful communication.

Providing All People with Equal Rights and Opportunities - Persons in all sorts of organisations as well as educational institutions at all levels, particularly those in leadership positions, must ensure that all individuals have equal rights and opportunities. All students should be given opportunity to monitor and improve their leadership abilities in the classroom. Employees should be given equal rights and chances to engage in various jobs and activities, as well as to voice their views and perspectives, in businesses. They will create motivation to carry out job responsibilities, achieve goals and objectives, and encourage communication procedures if they are given equal rights and chances. As a result, it can be claimed that ensuring equal rights and opportunities for all is critical in eliminating socio-psychological obstacles and effectively encouraging communication processes.

Nobody is being discriminated against - Discrimination against persons on the basis of caste, creed, race, religion, ethnicity, occupation, gender, age, or socioeconomic status is considered improper. Individuals in leadership roles within corporations and educational institutions must provide equal rights and opportunities for all employees and not discriminate against anybody based on the aforementioned considerations. Individuals who believe that equal rights and chances will assist them in performing their job obligations and reaching professional objectives will not only experience joy and fulfilment, but will also be able to overcome socio-psychological obstacles and encourage efficient communication. As a result, it can be argued that not discriminating against anybody is important in eliminating socio-psychological obstacles and encouraging well-organized communication processes.

Providing Appropriate Evaluation - Appropriate evaluation is considered essential for overcoming socio-psychological obstacles and encouraging successful communication. Individuals' performance must be evaluated by instructors and supervisors in both businesses and educational institutions. Individuals must use appropriate evaluation techniques and strategies in order to carry out the evaluation procedures in a meaningful manner. Methods and tactics must be in line with work performance, the outputs that must be produced, and goals and objectives that might be organisational or academic in character. Individuals promote communication processes in a well-organized manner when suitable assessment is offered. As a result, thorough evaluation is critical for overcoming socio-psychological obstacles and effectively boosting communication processes.

Norms and Principles for Information Generation - It is well recognised that inculcating moral and ethical values in persons is critical for promoting communication processes and overcoming hurdles. Individuals will develop knowledge in terms of norms and principles once they understand the meaning and relevance of morality and ethics. Morality, ethics, standards, and values are taught to children from an early age in order to promote good contact with all people. Individuals will be able to efficiently execute communication processes and overcome socio-psychological barriers if they create knowledge and put norms and principles into practise. As a result, it can be concluded that creating information in terms of norms and principles is essential for overcoming socio-psychological obstacles and encouraging productive communication processes.

V. CONCLUSION

To a large degree, socio-psychological obstacles play a vital role in imposing unfavourable consequences on communication processes. On the other hand, they play an important role in creating confrontational circumstances among people. These are in charge of the socio-psychological closure, which opposes and hinders the performance of further information that may potentially enhance the adoption of ideas and lead to the pacifying processes. The general functioning of organisations and educational institutions is influenced by socio-psychological obstacles. Both the senders and the receivers have difficulty effectively transmitting the information. Individuals' mental states have a significant impact on how they communicate with one another. Attitudes and opinions, emotions, status differences, inattention, closed mind, distrust, poor recollection, premature evaluation, interruption, and lack of feedback are all key socio-psychological obstacles to communication.

Individuals must develop knowledge in terms of strategies for overcoming socio-psychological barriers to communication. Having information about technologies, implementing broadmindedness, developing social skills, acquiring training, forming positive viewpoints in terms of all individuals, implementing interruption-prevention measures, providing equal rights and opportunities to all, not discriminating against anyone, providing proper evaluation, and generating information in terms of norms and principles are some of these. Finally, it can be concluded that when people execute these methods in a well-organized manner, they will be able to overcome socio-psychological barriers and enhance productive communication processes.

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